

METHODICAL DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING OF PRIMARY EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article examines the importance of professionally oriented pedagogical training aimed at developing students' critical thinking. Also, a summary of the curriculum for the development of critical thinking of future primary education teachers will be highlighted.

Key words: critical thinking, pedagogical training, educational system, methodology, mental activity, principle.

Introduction.

The priority task of a higher pedagogical educational institution should be the professional training of a modern teacher, including the ability to adapt to the conditions of the information society, to find optimal ways to solve complex problems, as well as to acquire knowledge independently to improve their professional level. All of the above can be provided when future professionals have the ability to think critically. At the current stage of the society's development, the indicator of the state's national wealth is intellectual resources, so the development prospects of any country are determined by the level and quality of education of its citizens. Special attention should be paid to the professional formation of the future primary education teacher as a subject of moral and ethical responsibility for the level of education of the citizens of the future democratic society.

The concept of critical thinking is considered in the work "The phenomenon of critical thinking in domestic and foreign scientific works", in which we give a detailed integrated definition of the phenomenon under study. Critical thinking as a mental activity of analysis, comparison, control, objective evaluation, proof and the ability to reject, is the ability to understand the truth or falsity of statements. Critical thinking is a characteristic of the teacher's personality. It is characterized by curiosity, a certain level of awareness and flexibility, to produce assumptions and to check them, is able to search for causes and anticipate consequences, can question what has become unclear. helps to improve oneself.

Researchers suggest various methods of forming this important professional quality, which can be divided into two directions: entering the educational process of the academic course "critical thinking", as well as forming critical thinking during the study of certain subjects.

We offer the author's technology for the formation of critical thinking in the process of professional training through the study of psychological and pedagogical sciences, the implementation of pedagogical practice and the implementation of professionally oriented pedagogical training.

The analysis of studies devoted to the consideration of this issue showed that the problem of using pedagogical training as a form of developing critical thinking in the process of professional training of future elementary teachers has not been sufficiently studied, it is a theoretical understanding and practical requires development.

Therefore, the purpose of the research is to theoretically and methodologically justify the possibility of using pedagogical technologies as a means of developing the critical thinking of future primary education teachers.

Researchers consider the concept of critical thinking as follows:

- methods of learning or developing the ability to master a certain type of complex activity (for example, communication)¹;
- the method of reprogramming the model of human behavior and activity management, the process of creating new functional formations that control behavior;
- "a multi-functional method of changing the psychological phenomena of a person in order to harmonize professional and personal life";
- an organizational form of educational work that ensures the effective use of various pedagogical methods by creating a positive emotional environment in the group and is aimed at the formation of skills and competencies².

Professor A. Markova considers the concept of "professional training" as a system of effects and exercises aimed at developing, forming and correcting the necessary professional qualities in a person. Vocational training allows you to form the personality of a specialist, develop the necessary professional skills, expand professional skills taking into account the new demands of society.

It should be noted that it is difficult to separate the pedagogical nature of the training and its psychological impact, just as it is difficult to separate the pedagogical and psychological impact on the formation of the personality during the educational process. But still, what distinguishes psychological training from professionally oriented pedagogical training? First, defining tasks related to pedagogical goals. Second, pedagogical training includes the use of pedagogical methods and techniques, which will be discussed later.

Analyzing the works devoted to educational forms of organizing the pedagogical process, we came to the conclusion that the conceptual basis of training is person-oriented, activity-based, dialogic, reflective approaches. The person-oriented approach includes the study of the student's value relationship to his personality, the mechanisms of his self-development, comes from the recognition of the uniqueness of the student's experience, and the second (*that is, the experience*) of the educational process considers it as a source of cognitive activity of the subject.

The theory of the activity approach is that the training and development of a future specialist takes place during his active activity: the acquisition of information through action is about 90%. The dialogue approach includes verbal formulation of thoughts, improvement of communicative interaction skills, stimulation of feedback among dialogue participants.

The tasks of professionally oriented pedagogical training determined by the target component are as follows:

- 1) introduce students to the essence of the concept of "critical thinking";
- 2) to help future teachers to understand the importance of forming critical thinking as a necessary professional importance of a modern specialist in the field of education;

¹ Emelyanov Yu. N. Active social and psychological training. L.: Leningrad State University, 1985. 4 p.

² Micheal A.V. Development of professional competence of specialists using paradigmatic modeling (interactive training): textbook. method. allowance. M., 2006. 130 p.

3) formation of skills, abilities, qualities, attitudes necessary for the implementation of critical thinking in students.

The structure of the author's professionally oriented pedagogical activity includes a series of lessons (*17 lessons of 2 hours*), each of which consists of three stages.

At the first stage, a positive atmosphere is created, the rules of working in a group are repeated, homework is discussed; the topic of the current lesson is reported, motivational introduction of the participants to the work is provided. At the beginning of the lesson, an exercise is carried out, which involves adapting the participants to mutual relations. Such exercises create an atmosphere of trust, goodwill and stress relief. The next point is reflection (or discussion) on the results of homework.

In the second stage, students acquire certain knowledge; they form the skills and abilities given by the purpose of the lesson. It will be discussed after the exercises. Acceptance of incomplete action can be used to encourage creative search activity among participants. Information blocks - messages, explanations (1-2 minutes), mini-lectures (7-15 minutes) are used to provide participants with the necessary information on the problem.

Let's dwell on specific examples of training methods and methods, which include: mini-discussions, essays, exercises, brainstorming, etc. Critical Thinking: Pros and Cons Mini-Discussion. Approximate questions for discussion: what should be the mindset of a modern person in the information society? Does a totalitarian society need thinking citizens? Can a democratic society exist without people capable of critical thinking? How does critical thinking benefit a person?

Mini-debate Can a teacher be non-political? Suggested discussion questions: Should a teacher express his or her own perspective on what is happening in his or her country? Do the teacher's values influence his/her performance? How can you influence social processes as a future professional?

Essay on Guiding Questions: Am I tolerant of different points of view? Do I have enough intellectual flexibility to avoid dogmatism? Am I able to accept the criticism necessary for my personal and professional development?

"Mental attack": what makes a person tolerant of others: pros and cons.

Students also keep an "achievement diary". Instructions: think about what you have achieved in your life and what you can add to such a diary. Write or draw your achievements. Try to post at least one small achievement every day.

Thinking Task: Do you agree that "a man who lacks the ability to think properly is not a free man" (J. Devi)? Or with the following statement: madness is that all men must be of the same opinion about some things (Voltaire).

The final stage involves students' awareness of the positive experience of participating in the lesson through personal and professional reflection. In addition, students usually receive homework aimed at deepening knowledge, strengthening and improving skills learned in class. Such tasks can be as follows: choose examples of stereotypes that exist in our life; pay attention to the manifestation of manipulations in the pedagogical process (prepare specific examples for discussion in the next lesson), observe the manifestations of intolerance and try to explain the reasons for their appearance; formation of life and professional faith, etc.

It should be noted that the training is aimed at influencing and developing the group by optimizing forms of interpersonal communication [ibid., p. 9]. During the dialogue, students

hear different points of view and their arguments, which allows them to check their opinions with the opinions of others. The successful actions of training participants are supported by the appropriate reaction of the group. During the group activity, feedback is made between the participants. The knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in the lesson are used in further joint work, as well as strengthened in the own experiences of future professionals to help develop all aspects of the personality of the future primary school teacher.

Professionally oriented pedagogical training, developed as a form of interaction between the participants of the educational process, not only allowed students to get the necessary information about the nature of critical thinking and the mechanism of its implementation, but also provided a future starting point. helped to form the personal and professional qualities of the inner school teacher. The above principles should include: the principle of confidentiality, the essence of which is to prohibit the release of statements heard from others outside the group work, which creates an atmosphere of trust, the principle of voluntary participation in the group work, which alleviates the psychological stress of the participants.

It should also be noted that traditional teaching methods only expand the scope of knowledge, but do not lead to a change in behavior. The positive aspect of the training program is that the participants do not focus on the need to acquire knowledge. Their acquisition is a specific effect of educational activities, and its important results are the change of semantic relations, the development of the future teacher's personal and professional values, and his professional skills.

Conclusion. The professionally oriented pedagogical activity developed as a form of interaction between the participants of the educational process not only allowed students to get the necessary information about the nature of critical thinking and the mechanism of its implementation, but also lajak helps to form the personal and professional qualities of the primary education teacher.

References:

- 1.Emelyanov Yu. N. Active social and psychological training. L.: Leningrad State University, 1985. 4 p.
- 2.Micheal A.V. Development of professional competence of specialists using paradigmatic modeling (interactive training): textbook. method. allowance. M., 2006. 130 p.
- 3.Yasvin V. A. Educational environment: from modeling to design. 2nd ed., rev. and additional M.: Smysl, 2001. 366 p.
- 4.Khudoynazarov, E. (2023). Boshlang'ich ta'limda mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. Молодые ученые, 1(13), 32-37.
- 5.Эгамберган, X. M. (2023). Ўқувчиларда танқидий фикрлашни ривожлантиришнинг педагогик ва методик асослари. Zamonaviy fan, ta'lim va ishlab chiqarish muammolarining innovatsion yechimlari, 4, 56-59.
- 6.Madraximovich, X. E., & Urazboyevna, U. N. (2023). O'quvchilar mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishda sinfdan tashqari ustoz-shogird munosabatlarining ahamiyati. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 12), 564-566.

- 7.Худайназаров, Э., & Куделько, Т. А. (2023). Интерактивные задания на английском языке для студентов с использованием футбольных метафор. Образование в сложном нестабильном мире, 83.
- 8.Худайназаров, Э. Д., & Куделько, Т. А. (2022). Школа будущего (по материалам опроса школьников России и Туркменистана). In Актуальные проблемы изучения иностранных языков и литератур (pp. 158-163).
- 9.Davronovich, B. M. (2021). Practical work in primary mathematics education as a methodological basis for the study of mathematics. Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research, 10(6), 173-176.
- 10.Madraximovich, K. E. (2020). Improving the methodological training of primary school teachers on the basis of innovative approaches. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 8(7).
- 11.Худойназаров, Э. М., & Бобожонов, А. Б. Синфдан ташқари ишларда ўқувчиларида мантиқий фикрлашни ривожлантиришнинг иновацион жиҳатлари.
- 12.Худойназаров, Э. М., Эсонов, Н. А., & Кучкаров, М. У. Преимущества альтернативных методов обучения.
- 13.Ткаченко Л. И. Феномен критического мышления в отечественных и зарубежных научных трудах // Научные записки. Серия «Психолого-педагогические науки». Нежин: НГУ им. Н. Гоголя, 2011. № 8. С. 15-19.
- 14.Гладышев С. Как вести себя на тренинге? // Обучение & карьера. 2005. № 35. С. 70-78.
- 15.Марасанов Г. И. Социально-психологический тренинг. М.: Совершенство, 1998. 13 с.
- 16.Щербаков А. В. Педагогический тренинг в индивидуализации подготовки студентов к воспитательной работе в школе: автореф. дисс. ... к. пед. н.: 13.00.08. Челябинск, 2000. 11 с.

